

SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT OF ATTINGAL MUNICIPALITY KERALA, INDIA-A CASE STUDY

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Abstract: Solid waste management is a critical component of sustainable urban development and environmental protection particularly in rapidly growing areas. This abstract provides an overview of key aspects related to solid waste management in Attingal Municipality, highlighting its importance, challenges, and strategies. Effective solid waste management encompasses collection, transportation, disposal, and recycling of waste materials to minimize environmental impact and promote public health. This study not only more insightful but also offer a clear, structured approach for both short-term action and long-term planning. Challenges in this field include the growing volume of waste, improper disposal methods, and limited resources for waste infrastructure. Sustainable solutions involve adopting innovative technologies, promoting waste reduction, and fostering community engagement. This abstract underscore the urgency of addressing solid waste management to create cleaner, healthier, and more sustainable communities.

Keywords: Solid waste management, Kerala, Scrap waste, Waste to energy

INTRODUCTION

Most human actions inevitably result in waste, which is a given together with mortality and change in our lives. Even though we cannot stop these events, we can enrich our preparedness by improving management [1]. Solid waste is the unwanted or of no utility matter originated from residential, industrial, and commercial activities in a given region. The different categories of solid waste are classified according to source including domestic, industrial, commercial, constructional, or institutional; by content, like organic materials, glass, metal, plastic, paper, and so on, or by potential for reuse, food waste, fabrics, rubber, leather, and debris from demolition and construction are all solid wastes. These are generally solids or semi-solids and people have disposed of them by either tossing them away or by incinerating them. Industrial waste is the one that is generated from manufacturers or commercial houses, while municipal solid waste is the one that has been generated in households and commercial houses [2]. Factors affecting the generation rate of garbage include population density, economic status, commercial activities, cultural norms, and the specific city or region under which the garbage is being produced. [3]. According to data from the World Bank, 2.01 billion tonnes of MSW are produced annually around the world, and of this trash, around one-third is handled and disposed of in a way that doesn't harm the environment. The majority of developed nations use techniques that are safe for the environment. According to Joseph et al., [4] the composition of MSW changes depending on a number of factors, such as geography, source, site of collection, and lifestyle habitats. Nearly 1.3 billion tons of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) is produced annually and is predicted to double up to 2.2 billion tons by 2025 globally. Solid wastes are categorized into organic waste, paper waste, plastic waste, glass waste, metal waste and other wastes [5, 6]. The major characteristics of hazardous waste are corrosiveness, ignitability, reactivity,

toxicity and these are waste materials that pose severe harm or can be fatal when ingested or absorbed into the body. [7]

Table 1. Shows solid waste category with examples

Solid Waste Category	Examples
Organic waste	Food scraps, yard leaves, grass, brush, wood, process residues paper, etc
Paper waste	Paper scraps, cardboard, newspapers, magazines, bags, boxes, wrapping paper, telephone books, shredded paper, paper beverage cups, etc. (typically managed separately)
Plastic waste (PW)	Bottles, packaging, containers, bags, lids, and cups made from various types of plastic
Glass waste	Glass bottles, broken glassware, light bulbs, coloured glass, etc.
Metal waste	Cans, foil, tins, non-hazardous aerosol cans, railings, bicycles, etc.
Other waste	Textiles, leather, rubber, multi-laminates, electronic waste (e-waste), appliances, ash, other inert materials, etc.

SOLID WASTE GENERATION IN INDIA

As per the annual report by CPCB, India generated 160,038.9 TPD of solid waste in the fiscal year 2020-21. Of this, an enormous amount of 152,749.5 TPD has been collected, which is 95.4 percent. According to this report, 50 percent, or 79,956.3 TPD, was treated. On the other hand, 18.4 percent, or 29,427.2 TPD, was landfilled. Interestingly, 50,655.4 TPD, which constitutes 31.7 percent of the total wastes sent to landfill are not accounted for. The percentage of processing of solid waste has risen from 19 percent recorded in 2015-16 over the last five years to nearly 50 percent in 2020-21. Landfills disposal has reduced from 54 percent in 2015-16 to 18.4 percent in 2020-21 [21].

SOLID WASTE GENERATION IN KERALA

Kerala, known as "God's Own Country," is a tropical peninsular state in western India with 38,863 km² of land area, or 1.2% of the country's total area. It is located between the northern latitudes of 8°.17'.30" and 12°.47'.40" N and the eastern longitudes of 74°.27'.47" and 77°.37'.12" E. The state is surrounded by land on three sides and by water on the fourth. The state is bounded by the Arabian Sea (Lakshadweep Sea) in the west, Tamil Nadu and the Indian Ocean in the south, the states of Karnataka on the north and north-east, and the state of Tamil Nadu in the east. About 560 kilometres of shoreline are present in the State. According to the Census of India 2011, Kerala had 3,34,06,061 residents, or 2.76 percent of all Indians. 52 percent of the people in the state are women, and 48 percent are men. Kerala had the lowest decadal population growth rate of all the Indian States at 4.9 percent. Total waste generated in the State is around 15000 tons per day at 450 grams per capita per day. It is expected that the future waste generation will be more in central and northern parts of the State as compared to the Southern part. Kerala produces around 11,449 tonnes of solid trash every day, with 3,452 tonnes coming from urban regions and

7,997 tonnes coming from rural ones, according to the Kerala State Environment Plan 2022 and Kerala also produces 3.7 million tonnes of solid trash per year.

Solid Waste Management:

Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) is a systematic process that encompasses the collection, processing, and disposal of solid waste as well as the storage, transportation, and resource recovery. Management of municipal solid waste is crucial because, if not handled effectively, it has negative effects on society's aesthetics, ecology, and health. [8] Waste management practices differ for developed and developing nations, for urban and rural area, and for residential and industrial producers. Poor management of waste and treatment and effluent disposal system, result, in potential public health risk [9]. A comprehensive solid waste management strategy encompasses a range of activities aimed at minimizing environmental impact, ensuring public health and safety, and optimizing resource recovery through proper handling, segregation, collection, transportation, storage, recycling, disposal, and treatment of solid waste. Each activity plays a vital role in the overall waste management process [10]. Poor management of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) contributes to various kinds of pollution including the air, soil, and water. The negligent disposal of waste has contaminated surface and groundwater sources. MSW accumulates in metropolitan cities due to which stagnated water, often serving as a breeding ground for insects, causes floods during the rainy seasons. Furthermore, the uncontrolled burning of such wastes. The main causes of urban air pollution are the improper burning of MSW. The decomposition of organic waste in landfills results in greenhouse gases, and the untreated leachate coming from these dumps contaminates the soil and sources of water near them. Moreover, improper MSW management raises health and safety issues. Waste attracts rats and insects, which might cause diseases like cholera and dengue fever [11,22].

The waste management system in Kerala reflects its commitment to sustainable development and environmental conservation. However, the effectiveness of these initiatives may vary across different regions of the state. Effective solid waste management attempts to lessen or eliminate negative effects on the environment, human health, and economic growth while fostering a higher standard of living. Monitoring, collecting, transportation, processing, recycling, and disposal are just a few of the critical procedures involved in managing municipal garbage (Manoj, 2017).

The fundamental principles of waste management include three objectives:

1. Management of urban solid waste management used to protect the health of the urban population especially the health of the low- and middle-income groups.
2. Should be to protect the environment by controlling water and soil pollution it should also ensure the sustainable management.

3. By offering effective waste management services and guaranteeing the effective use and conservation of movable materials and resources, to assist urban economic development.

Kerala grapples with the daunting challenge of managing a daily waste output exceeding 8000 tons, with plastic waste constituting 7% of this total. This predicament has left every town and city in the state struggling to cope with the mounting piles of solid waste, as disposal options remain limited. As one traverses from the northern to the southern regions of Kerala, it becomes evident that the landscape is marred by numerous garbage hotspots. Locations like Kelugudde, Seethangoli, and Kollangana in Kasargod; Pettippalam and Chelora in Kannur; Njeliyaparamba in Kozhikode; Pirivusala in Palakkad; Lalur in Thrissur; Chakkukandam in Guruvayur; Brahmapuram in Ernakulam; Vadavathur in Kottayam; Fathimapuram near Changanassery; Kanaathupaara near Pala; Kozhenchery in Pathanamthitta; Kureepuzha in Kollam; and Vilappilsala in Thiruvananthapuram are just a few of these hotspots. In response, local resistance movements have emerged to protest against the indiscriminate dumping of solid waste, including plastic and electronic waste, a byproduct of Kerala's relentless march toward urbanization [12,13].

The waste management profile of Kerala comprises 6 Municipal Corporations, 87 municipalities, 77 Taluks, 14 District Panchayats, 152 Block Panchayats, and 941 Grama Panchayats. Annually, the state produces a total 3.7 million tons of solid waste, which is composed of 69% biodegradable waste and 31% non-biodegradable waste. The biodegradable waste contains about 70% moisture content. The remaining waste in this non-biodegradable sector can be categorized further into combustible 79.2% and non-combustible fractions. At a production rate of 0.28 kg of waste per head daily, Kerala's municipalities produce a large volume of waste. According to projections by the Urban Development Section of the World Bank, garbage-producing heads should increase at an exponential growth rate of 1.41% every year. Thus, it can be said that in the present era every human being produces 0.343 kg MSW per day, as a whole 7056 tons of MSW are produced daily basis. [14]. It is estimated that today Kerala produces over 8000 tonne wastes per day out of which 7% is plastic waste. Due to which today, every city and town in the state cannot cater to the solid wastes that are produced day by day because it lacks disposal options [15].

Attingal Municipality is situated at Chirayinkeezh taluk, Thiruvananthapuram district. Total number of wards 31 and the population of the Municipality is 38,838. Attingal Urban Renewal Committee was formed in 1919 and it became a Municipality in 1922. [16] The latitude of Attingal is 8.695034, and the longitude is 76.817879. Attingal is located at the towns place category with the GPS coordinates of 8° 41' 42.1224" N and 76° 49' 4.3644" E.. Kanyakumari-Panvel Road is one of the main roads NH66 with SH46 and SH47 link Klimanur and Venjarammodu pass through the town. SH 46 accession is located at Alamcode and SH 47 at Munumukku, a place of high traffic density.[17]

Fig 1: Shows the map of Attingal Municipality- Source: [18]

SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN ATTINGAL MUNICIPALITY

Attingal municipality, like all other municipalities in Kerala, faces critical issues in the production and management of solid wastes. The various steps in the SWM of the municipality, which range from waste collection to transportation and disposal to recycling etc, still contain a number of gaps that need to be adequately addressed for total sustainability.

In Attingal Municipality, the collection is carried out through a door-to-door method by members of Kudumbashree units, covering every ward across the municipality. Residents are encouraged to separate waste into two categories - biodegradable and non-biodegradable. However, such compliance level differs from one resident to another. There are particular public bins within which wastes are to be dropped in some regions. Mini Material Collection Facilities (MCF) are set up at the ward level to store segregated waste temporarily before further processing or transportation. Municipal waste management vehicles are used to transport waste from the Mini MCFs to the central processing facility. This step is crucial for managing the flow of waste within the municipality. At the central composting site, biodegradable waste is processed in conversion of organic material into compost, which is then sold or used locally in agriculture. Regrettably, the capacities of the composting facilities are commonly under-capacity and thus cannot process the volumes of organic waste generated. Non-biodegradable waste is the other type of waste mainly processed through recycling, though proper sorting and recycling infrastructure is underdeveloped, and a huge proportion of recyclables end up in landfills. The main disposal method for non-recyclable waste is landfilling. The volume of waste often causes the landfill site nearby the municipality to be jammed, leading to ground-water contamination, soil deterioration, and air pollution caused by the burning of wastes. [19,20,]

Moreover, ten scrap collection unit in Attingal municipality, which are frequently interacted with by people, were selected for this study. Among them, 5 are authorized by the Attingal municipality, while the other 5 are unauthorized. These are located in residential area. Such improper and proper units for collecting scraps raise serious concerns on issues of environmental management and the general health and safety of the public. Improper ones are unhygienic dumping of wastes, which may lead to hazardous conditions, affecting the local ecosystem, as well as polluting urban areas. It is generally reflective of the broader issues that characterize developing towns with rapid population growths outpacing the infrastructural developments, hence the improper waste management systems [18]. The scrap collection units in Attingal comprise local informal workers. Scrap collection units at the different level operate by collecting scrap of different types coming from houses, businesses, and institutions. These scrap collection units collect, plastics like PET bottles, plastic bags, and containers; metals like tin waste of aluminium, iron and copper; paper and cardboard like newspapers, books, packing material and also E-waste like waste electronic products, which may encompass mobile phones, computers, and various household appliances.

When we need material collected up, we give the scrap collectors a call; alternatively, the collectors might visit a certain region on a regular basis. The collectors purchase scrap from residents, based on weight and variety, so thereby giving residents an economic incentive to segregate and sell their recyclables. Scrap is sorted by type of material once it has been collected, either at the small points of collection or at the warehouses of the scrap dealers. Sorting by labours, wherein materials are cleaned and sorted in categories that can be sold to recycling plants. Generally, these units of scrap act as middlemen and sell large volumes of sorted materials to larger recycling firms or facilities in nearby cities. Major problem noted behind this is majority of the scrap materials are stored in open spaces and uncovered, which causes leaching of numerous pollutants more than that they transport the scrap materials to the recycling site according to the quantity and scrap rate increases. This is the reason why the scrap materials may be left in the scrap collection unit for a long time and also cause environmental problems.

For the intervention to Attingal Municipality, would be short-term implementation of door-to-door waste collection, encouraging source segregation at-source, erecting education programs that enhance public participation in recycling; infrastructure investment in waste-to-energy plants, large-scale composting facilities, embracing advanced technologies such as AI use for waste sorting and processing that can decrease landfill usage over time, this allow clear, structured approaches for both short-term action and long-term planning. This would therefore make it possible for the stakeholders to rank their resources and efforts better for sustainable solid waste management in Attingal Municipality. By integrating AI into waste management services, Attingal Municipality can optimize costs, improve environmental impact through enhanced recycling and waste reduction, elevate service quality, and make

data-driven decisions for long-term sustainability. These AI-driven initiatives can enhance solid waste management systems and propel the municipality towards a more sustainable future.

CHALLENGES & RECOMMENDATIONS

Major challenges in scrap waste management in Attingal municipality are,

1. **Inadequate segregation at source:** Households and business firms segregate only to some extent by separating organic, recyclable, and scrap, but scrap usually goes along with other forms of wastes, which makes recycling tough.
2. **Irregular collection and transport schedules:** It leads to improper disposal by residents, such as dumping in public spaces or burning.
3. **Public awareness:** Nobody is worried or nobody is bothered about scrap waste, public awareness is essential to waste whether it's emitting odour or it's odourless it can cause same impact.
4. **Informal Sector Dominance:** Scrap waste management is often handled by the informal sector (e.g., scrap dealers and rag-pickers), who may not have proper facilities for safe and environmentally sound.
5. **Less availability of recyclers:** The location may have lower availability of scrap recycling centres within or nearby Attingal.
6. **Health hazards and Environmental pollution:** causes environmental pollution due to inappropriate scrap waste management, especially on electronic or hazardous scrap waste.

Recommendations for Improvement are,

1. **Awareness Campaigns and Education Programs:** Organize education campaigns in schools, different communities, and through media to encourage the source separation and segregation of waste.
2. **Improved Collection Systems:** A separate collection system for scrap material must be mapped out and established. Dedicated scrap collection days must be allocated, and individuals must know about the scheduled dates of collection.
3. **Collaboration with the informal sector:** Engaging scrap dealers and rag-pickers in formalized systems for managing wastes.
4. **Local recycling infrastructure:** Installing local recycling units that recycle scrap locally at source and decrease long-distance transport.
5. **Incentive Programs:** Introduce incentive programs targeting households and businesses for awards when they successfully manage their scrap through recycling.

CONCLUSION

In Attingal Municipality, the scrap collection mechanism forms an important but informal element of the local infrastructure, unplanned processing of scrap waste leads to major problems. Nobody is worried or nobody is bothered. So, it's necessary to create or propose an efficient system to manage these scrap collection units and to make sure the scrap is not dumped for prolonged period that will periodically result in heavy pollution. After proposing an efficient system and helping the concerned authorities to implement it. Like to create an awareness campaign among public through my research that the waste whether it's emitting odour or it's odourless it can cause same impact and people should urge for a solution to concerned authorities and hope to bring a change. So, it's a relevant subject due to its environmental impact and very few studies been done focusing on this issue. It is necessary for people and businesses to know the importance of waste management.

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